

School Leaders and their Leadership Style: Does it Keep Them in the Role?

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Abstract

In a global context of school leader shortages, understanding how leadership styles influence job satisfaction and an individual's willingness to stay in the role is important. Now, as more Canadian schools are led by retired or temporary principals, the crisis of school leadership leavers, and the negative impact on school improvement must be deeply considered. Yet, with the erosion of defined authority and power, traditional managerial leadership approaches are considered less desirable by communities. At the same time, the expectations placed upon the principal is continuing to grow. Principals and vice principals must lead through gained permission and influence. The tension between stakeholders, principals' supervisors, and unions are making "doing the work" of the role increasingly complex. Most of today's principals opt for transformative, distributive or moral leadership styles. Others suggest situational transactive leadership styles are more common by action than by name. Whatever way you describe it, leading a school is a complex combination of influence, perceived power and care that few other professions require under such public scrutiny. Understanding which leadership styles allow principals to ethically lead their schools, while contributing to their job satisfaction and overall wellbeing would inform onboarding and mentoring programs for school leaders. This bounded study of 260 Ontario, Canada school leaders will explore whether particular leadership style influences job satisfaction or positional longevity intention.

Key words:

School leader, leadership style, principal, distributive leadership, transformative leadership, servitude leadership, transactional leadership, job satisfaction, retention

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Blanchard (2018) suggested that wellbeing, job satisfaction, and retention, were deeply connected with administrator leadership style. The heart of leadership, as described by Sergiovanni and Green (2015), points to the importance of a moral drive aligning with an

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educator's beliefs. Donohoo (2017) provided great credence to the foundation of trust and building collective efficacy in learning communities. Leithwood and colleagues' (2017) work highlighted the importance of school leadership for a school's stability and student achievement. Now as more Canadian schools are led by retired or temporary principals, the crisis of school leadership leavers, and the negative impact on school improvement must be deeply considered. Yet, with the erosion of defined authority and power, traditional managerial or bureaucratic approaches to leadership are considered desirable by communities. At the same time, the expectations placed upon the principal is continuing to grow (McHolm, 2025a). Principals and vice principals must lead through gained permission and influence. Different administrators use these two types of power, impacting relationships and trust levels that they build with staff (Blanchard, 2018; Owens & Valesky, 2015; Sergiovanni & Green, 2015). The tension between stakeholders, principals' supervisors, and unions are making "doing the work" of the role increasingly complex. Most of today's principals opt for less autocratic or bureaucratic forms of leadership and more transformative, distributive or moral leadership styles (Owens & Valesky, 2015). Others suggest situational transactive leadership styles more common by action than by name. Whatever way you describe it, leading a school is a complex combination of influence, perceived power and care that few other professions require under such public scrutiny (Kutsyurba et al. 2024). Understanding which leadership styles allow principals to ethically lead their schools, while contributing to their job satisfaction and overall wellbeing would inform onboarding and mentoring programs for school leaders. This study will explore whether particular leadership style influences job satisfaction or positional longevity intention.

The primary distinctions in leadership styles relate to authority and influence. Extensive research has been completed on bureaucratic, personal, professional, and moral leadership styles (Sergiovanni & Green, 2015). Proffit (2015) refined Sergiovanni and Green's (2015) work to include bureaucratic authority, psychological authority, technical-rational authority, professional authority, and moral authority. Each has a purpose and a context where its use will garner greater results. Proffit (2015) proved that leaders need to be aware of the differences in authority types and should select a specific approach for a specific situation. The choice of authority-style interactions is highly subjected to a leader's emotional and personal investment in the outcome of a decision (Ollo-López et al., 2016; Ozer, 2013; Palmerston, 2016; Pollock & Edge, 2017).

Research has supported the importance of fit of the leadership style to the organizational culture. This relies on the fact that leaders significantly influence attitude and motivation of their teachers (Sadiartha & Sitorus, 2018). School districts need to consider not only how principals and vice principals impact school-based job satisfaction (Hoxha & Hyseni-Duraku, 2017; Nazim & Mahmood, 2018), but also how directors and superintendents influence leadership practices at those sites (Parylo & Zepeda, 2015).

Rapid shifts in the social constructs of morality and “popularism” have challenged leadership styles, as there is no one acceptable definition of morality or values to all of society. This makes moral leadership even more complex than understanding the difference between right and wrong and upholding the values of a community (Çelik, 2014). Howard (2015) described moral leadership as the combination of virtues to character, including integrity, discernment, love, respect, humility, diligence, temperance, and courage. When these desirable dispositions are combined, a moral leader is able to navigate the emotional landscape of decision making in contentious scenarios (Blanchard, 2018). One who leads from a place of servitude requires greater emotional labour to perform the job and often experiences higher levels of intrinsic motivation (Maxwell & Riley, 2017). Leading from this stance requires more cognitive and emotional commitment to any particular situation.

Selecting the appropriate style of authority in the context of a learning organization is essential to advancing a school toward the shared responsibility of decision making and collective efficacy (Donohoo, 2017). We saw an acceptance of more procedurally based leadership through the pandemic (Kutsyurba et al. 2024) and by extension, directive leadership represented a sense of stability and trustworthiness for some school communities. If a school needs that structure of bureaucratic leadership, then using a professional or moral style would feel disconnected for staff / families with a lack of clarity. Using one approach over another style of leadership is the recognition that schools need different things at different times, seasonally or episodically. Seasonally high stress times, such as report cards, teachers need more bureaucratic approaches to leadership. Similarly, during traumatic stress or events within a school community, reverting back to the policies and procedures might be necessary to support the community through its grieving process grounded in the consistency of logic. For some leaders and their staff, this would seem impersonal. At times, a leader must differentiate his or her leadership approach to promote mental wellbeing alongside functional compliance. It takes a skilled administrator to know when each form of authority would be most effective (Sergiovanni & Green, 2015). Unexpectedly, Cabuhat (2023) found that both transformative and

transactional styles of leadership had similar implications on staff satisfaction. Therefore, a more pragmatic approach to leadership could potentially harness the best results for the school. Exploring the adaptive nature and a breadth of approaches are necessary for educational leaders to manage the diverse needs of their buildings. Yet, transitioning through forms of authority or leadership styles can create higher levels of emotional labour, mental exhaustion, and at times, feeling of disingenuousness (Kutsyurba et al. 2024). Those outside of the role may judge harshly, adding to feelings of scrutiny stress or lower senses of recognition (Rice & Williams, 2022).

Stakeholders have expectations about leadership approaches. Schmidt et al. (2018) indicated that staff members expect employee-centered support. Stakeholders increasingly want active involvement in resolving situations, which from a workload perspective, increases time dedicated to competing issues. Yet, without that approach, more research indicated that teacher performance and wellbeing are negatively affected (Katz, Dack, & Malloy, 2018). Within the Ontario, Canada context, contractual restrictions limit formal involvement in collective meetings to once a month, thereby creating less efficient opportunities to influence decisions and gather information. Lee and Kuo (2019) noted that school leaders are increasingly expected to be a super or exceptional principal, making the role more challenging for everyone. Studies based on Canada's top principals also echo these findings of superheroes in the role (Kutsyurba et al. 2024).

Leadership styles can no longer be unidimensional (Blanchard, 2018). The role of school administrator is far too complex to be able to respond to all situations with a singular approach of bureaucratic, autocratic, transactional, and distributive or even through servitude or moral leadership (Edge et al, 2017). The reality is that within specific contexts, a school principal or vice principal must select the approach that will reach the end goal in the most humane way and that will allow those stakeholders to move forward (Smagorinsky, 2024). An administrator's leadership style impacts his or her connectedness and relatedness, competence, and autonomy (Andriansyah, 2023; Chang et al., 2015). These factors then interplay with their sense of wellbeing and perceptions of life balance.

Literature Review

The literature shows that principals have a strong influence, second only to teachers, for improving student achievement (Leithwood et al., 2017). It also has been shown that lower socioeconomic features of a school increase the importance of the school leaders. In schools

with stronger economic features, leadership is less important. Leadership style impacts all aspects of the principal or vice principal's day. How they make decisions, how they interact with students, staff, families and community members are all influenced by their beliefs on their role and how they should lead.

Over the last 2 decades considerable attention has been spent on various aspects of school leadership. In this highly demanding role, school leaders must put in long hours, deal with complex situations and flow between distinctly different contexts. If working within publicly-funded school districts, administrators do not have the autonomy to select schools that they feel well matched to. We also know that job satisfaction is high within the profession. This, then is more about their leadership style, the belief in the importance of the role and the values they bring to the job.

Across large studies, not all types of school leadership lead to job satisfaction. The most efficacious form is transformative leadership coupled with collective efficacy. Leithwood and Sun (2018) linked transformative leadership behaviours with increased job satisfaction scores by 43% and higher teacher empowerment. This showed a significant positive correlation ($r = .67, p < .001$). Most interesting is that study sources did find consistently that a particular style of leadership led to higher job satisfaction. There is limited research comparing various leadership styles and job satisfaction. There is also a gap in educational research related to leadership styles and leaving data. What studies showed was if the principal is able to promote collaboration, trust and community engagement, those principals tend to have higher levels of job satisfaction and lower signs of burnout. It is these factors, that in turn lead to higher intentions of staying in the role (Heenan et al., 2024; Hickey et al., 2022).

Distributive leadership is one that trusts those that work for them. This leader develops staff to take on distinct roles and empower individuals to lead. Distributive leadership styles also offered strong job satisfaction, but through the lens of work-life balance. When you develop a team of engaged individuals, then the workload is more manageable. Distributive leadership also lowers rates of burnout or exhaustion (DeMatthews et al. 2021). Sharing the workload also improves shared purpose and reduces burnout (Hickey et al., 2022). Heenan and colleagues (2024) emphasized that distributive leadership enhances collaboration and trust. This, in turn, strengthens community relationships and creates a positive school climate. Distributive leadership also fosters professional growth and staff satisfaction (Sindhvad et al. 2020). But perhaps most importantly for this study, it leads to higher rates of principal retention, as it

addresses one of the biggest areas that single administrators face – isolation and feeling unsupported (DeMatthews et al. 2021).

Forms of servant or servitude leadership predicated on putting the needs of others over your own. Leaders that follow this approach tend to have elevated levels of job satisfaction and wellbeing (Eva & Sendjaya, 2024). This stands to reason as when things are difficult, it connects with the purpose of their position (Blanchard, 2018). Because principals with this leadership style want to see their impact on staff and student wellbeing, they are encouraged to stay in the role. They also see a direct connection between their work and the outcome on the school in general. This supports job satisfaction.

Situational or Purposeful Transactional Leadership is a style of leadership that suggests at times, some situations require leaders to approach in different ways. At times, an experienced school leader will need to employ different tactics to manage a circumstance. When done well, this leadership style can augment a leader's self-efficacy (Donohoo, 2017). This leadership style may appear manipulative to some, and may increase the need for surface acting or projecting an emotional response that is not congruent to the school leader's internal sentiment. Purposeful transactional leadership requires flexibility, the ability to see what is needed at a given time. Purposeful transactional or situational leadership styles help the principal look the rules and reinforces a predictable work environment. Transactional or situational leadership can create short-term or immediate job satisfaction on a case-by-case basis as it focuses on individual tasks, thereby making them more manageable. In a job that has unclear boundaries, keeping successes notable on the small and immediate scale could allow principals to stay in the role longer.

Authoritarian leadership models rely on the assumption of hierarchical power. The leader makes a decision (with or without consultation) and implements the decision. Policies and procedures are followed with less importance placed upon nuanced mitigating factors. It is based on a pre-determined set of rules that keeps things "fair". This style of leadership also can afford stability. During periods of rapid change or crisis (as experienced throughout the early stages of the pandemic), this approach to leadership made people feel that someone else had the answer. When individuals are overwhelmed, this directive style brought a sense of calm to individuals in schools. Unclear in this bounded study, if there was a link between leaving the role in this leadership style because most did not self-report this type of leadership style.

Adhering to one type of leadership is rare in today’s complex and everchanging schools (Cobiskey, 2024). School Leaders must be adaptive to the circumstance while maintaining their belief systems if they are to preserve their wellbeing (Heenan et al. 2024). Their professional resilience also showed enhancements if leaders could both identify the best course of action needed and enact it (Grissom et al., 2021a, 2021b; Heenan et al. 2024).

Table One compares different types of leadership styles looking at current research related to job satisfaction and the desire to stay in the role or not. Different methodologies pointed to different findings across leadership types amongst principals and school leaders. General trends showed that leadership styles that share decision making had a higher impact on positive engagement of staff, but also required more time. Under periods of high workflow and constraints related to shared decision making, leaders found that this could slow the progression of implementation or change dynamics. The vested interest of stakeholders could be the source of support and distributed responsibilities or equally act as a barrier to efficiency. Building and maintaining trust throughout these processes was essential to the success of the school leader.

Table 1

Comparison of Leadership Styles on Job Satisfaction, Staff Satisfaction, and Retention

Leadership Style	Principal Job Satisfaction	Staff Retention & Satisfaction	Influence on Principal’s Desire to Stay
Transformational Leadership Heenan, Lafferty, & McNamara (2024)	Generally high when integrated with distributed practices; fosters positive relationships, trust, and community engagement.	Increases staff satisfaction through shared vision and inclusive culture.	Principals motivated to stay when they experience positive community engagement and support.
Authoritarian / Bureaucratic Leadership	50% of those in study showed an authoritarian leadership style –	Study showed that staff may experience higher levels of dissatisfaction,	Study did not explore principal’s desire to stay or leave the role / or their job satisfaction.

(Stepanyan & Geghamyan, 2025)	centralized decision-making, strict hierarchies and limited teacher autonomy.	leading to higher turnover.	
Transactional Leadership	Satisfaction linked to clear expectations; may lead to satisfaction if roles are well-defined but can cause dissatisfaction due to lack of intrinsic motivation.	Staff retention may be moderate; effective in structured environments but may not foster engagement.	Principals may stay if transactional systems are effective but risk burnout from routine focus.
Distributed Leadership (Hickey et al., 2022)	Promotes principal satisfaction by sharing responsibilities, reducing workload, and fostering collaboration.	Staff satisfaction and retention improve due to empowerment and shared decision-making.	Principals more likely to stay when they work within supportive, collaborative environments.
Instructional Leadership (Dami et al. 2022)	High when principals feel effective in guiding teaching and learning; correlated with professional growth and higher job satisfaction.	Staff satisfaction increases when leadership supports professional development.	Principals tend to stay when they see positive student and staff outcomes. When principals are engaged, feel they have the skills to lead improvement, they are motivated to stay in the role.
Servant Leadership (Eva & Sendjaya, 2024)	Associated with higher principal satisfaction due to focus on	Staff retention and satisfaction improve through trust and	Principals motivated to stay when they see their impact on staff and student wellbeing.

	service, support, and ethical guidance.	organizational commitment.	
Transformational + Distributed Leadership (Heenan, Lafferty & McNamara, 2024)	Synergistic effects lead to high principal satisfaction through shared vision, community engagement, and reduced workload.	Staff satisfaction and retention are maximized in such environments.	Principals are more likely to remain when leadership practices foster trust, empowerment, and community.

Mediating Factors

We know that not all schools and communities are the same. Successful principals, using a specific approach can be successful in one type of school or culture but not be in another. Working conditions vary greatly, as do professional opportunities and support systems. In the bounded study of this article, the working conditions of the publicly funded schools and the privately funded schools had significant implications related to working conditions, working environments, hours of work, joys, types of dissatisfiers and their intensities.

Repeatedly in the research transformative, servitude and distributive leadership have the greatest levels of resiliency amongst school leaders (Eva & Sendjaya, 2024; Heenan et al. 2024). This is because these leadership approaches build trusting relationships and they foster positive connections and engagement. Putting the people that a leader works with first, over the school leader themselves leads to greater support. As the study showed, this commitment to the school over the impact on their personal wellbeing was a common aspect of the job (McHolm, 2025b). School principals expected that as part of the role, thereby making the efforts worth the pain. This was particularly true within the publicly funded school settings. The emotional labour of the role made the personal sacrifices warranted, “when I am doing something that is hard for me, but I can see the difference that it could make, I will do it – even if it may not be good for me in particular”. This emotional labour and dedication to the role did not resonate in the same way with school leaders in the private school system. For them, if the emotional labour was high, their enjoyment of the role decreased (McHolm, 2025a). By aligning the school leader’s expectations with the reality of the school that they are leading, then synergetic commitment will happen. When the right principal is not matched with the school community that drives them then frustration can mount. No leadership approach will correct

for that type of misfit, as one respondent said it this way, “I was placed at one of the most affluent schools in our district. But that was not where my heart lay. I wanted to be in a place where the kids really needed me. At School X, their families could give them everything and they treated me like I was the hired help”. Building community is an important aspect of the school leader, and when the fit is wrong, the leadership approach will not have the desired outcomes.

Support systems are critical when leading a school. From administrative support, human resource support (specialized staff), mentorship and skilled teaching staff all make important contributions. They not only have an impact on the students of the school, but on to a school leader’s job satisfaction (McHolm, 2025b). When a team comes together, they can overcome challenging situations. When an administrator is in a position of isolation or with limited support, then those challenges are more arduous to manage. In turn, lower levels of job satisfaction are experienced.

Instructional leadership is a condition of the role. When school leaders are given the opportunity to develop their skills in this area, they feel more confident in the role (DeMatthews et al., 2021; Sindhvad et al., 2020). Professional development is usually done within a community. This then also builds a support network, which acts as another insulating factor. The more that one knows the skills they are requiring their staff to complete, the better prepared they are lead a school.

Leadership Styles Really Matters

Across most studies, leadership styles’ impact on teacher’s wellbeing or job satisfaction was seen. The more decision-making, the more autonomy and the more influence on their specific jobs, led teachers to be happier. But the examination about the how leadership influences the leader has been less clearly studied.

Studies explored individual leadership styles using a number of frameworks from self-assessments, self-reports and teacher’s perceptions of leadership behaviours. Less common were the comparison of multiple leadership types (although some compared two types) in order to determine patterns of resilience, happiness and overall wellbeing. There was a trend that when staff is happy, then the leader tended to be more satisfied in their role. But at best, this was a correlational connection. Although it stands to reason, if a staff is content, then they are more willing to participate in the tasks that make a school run smoothly, they are more

willing to give their trust in seeing the longer-term plan that a leader may be wanting to go. Although this aspect of the principal's job satisfaction, it is only indirectly explored within this article.

What is clear, is that leadership styles reflect the person that is leading. They are a choice that a leader has. In a role with many dictated constraints, the principal's choice of leadership style is a combination of function, context and personality. Finding the right leadership style for the context will have a measurable impact on job satisfaction.

Leadership development programs make a difference to job satisfaction. They combine a sense of belonging, support and competence. When school leaders are given the professional development and the support to explore the expression of this training, leaders can adapt their approach more skillfully to various situations. Leaders know that the same approach may not be successful in all contexts. Helping leaders understand the merits, drawbacks and applicability of specific leadership styles are important for the maintenance of job satisfaction for school leaders.

Comparisons Leadership Style, Job Satisfaction and Staff Satisfaction

The research within the educational field points to many connections between leadership styles and job satisfaction. Most importantly is the link between the principal's style of leadership and not only the retention rate for that administrator, but also for the staff members that they serve. The Table below explores larger scale studies of the link between both the leader's job satisfaction and whether they stay in the role, but also how their leadership impacts staff satisfaction.

The Study

This article explores a smaller subset of a study completed in Ontario, Canada during the pandemic. At that time, publicly-funded and privately-funded administrators participated in the survey. Two populations were examined, publicly funded school administrators, through advertising in Ontario Principals Council ($n = 183$, $n = 32$) e-newsletter and privately funded Ontario provincially accredited school leader respondents ($n = 32$, $n = 8$). The combined population used for reliability testing and the principal component analysis was a sample size of $n = 215$. Including the qualitative data streams, there were 260 datasets within this study. Although the larger study explored the multi-faceted nature of wellbeing, job satisfaction and

positional longevity intentions, this subset wanted to determine if leadership style had any implications for job satisfaction and their commitment to the role.

The research questions posed were: Does a principal's leadership style influence their job satisfaction? Do specific types of leadership styles lead to stronger organizational commitments? Do specific leadership styles of school leaders change the experience of emotional labour / emotional drain? The results of this study were not what was expected by the researcher.

The participants were given definitions of the following leadership styles: Transformative, Purposeful Transactional / Situational, Servitude, Consultative, Distributive, Democratic, Moral, Consensus and Bureaucratic. The limitation of self-report may lead to inaccurate self-assessment. Equally important, most school leaders know that certain leadership styles are considered "more progressive" or "more ideal" and this may therefore influence their identification. As part of the questionnaire, it was asked, both what was their preferred approach and what was the approach that they took as a leader while under pressure.

Instrumentation

This study employed an original questionnaire developed by adapting and expanding the COPSOQ III framework. While maintaining core elements that measure job satisfaction, workplace commitment, and organizational commitment across 18 dimensions, the instrument was modified to address specific aspects of educational leadership. The job security dimension was removed as it was not relevant to the Ontario, Canada context as we are experiencing a shortage of school principals and vice principals.

The questionnaire incorporated elements from the COPSOQ II long form, particularly regarding emotional labour and wellbeing, which were not present in the COPSOQ III short form. They were tested for validity and reliability, matching that of the original two questionnaires.

Additionally, sections were added to examine the leadership background and school context of the school leaders. The author pondered if certain working environments directed leaders to utilize different leadership styles that were situationally specific. The questionnaire also considered the factors that influence retention and attrition rates of those school leaders.

The final instrument utilized both Likert scale and multiple-choice questions to capture quantitative data. Due to the substantial modifications to the original COPSOQ III and the

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inclusion of new elements, this questionnaire represents an original research tool designed specifically for this study, but with approvals granted from COPSOQ. For the purposes of this article, the results from the leadership background, leadership style and school context will be highlighted, while discussing how it might influence organizational commitment.

Software analysis utilized SPSS and NVivo.

Distribution of Leadership Styles Across School Contexts

School Principals and vice principals were asked to identify their most consistent leadership style from ten options. The most common leadership style was *Purposeful* or *Situational* leadership style. *Transformative* leadership is also well represented as the approach that almost a third of leaders use, followed by *Moral* and *Distributive* leadership styles. The least common leadership style among participants was a *Democratic* leadership style. No administrator selected this leadership style as their most typical approach. Within the fast-paced, large number of students, staff and stakeholders, such an approach would be both time consuming and would not lead to the most informed decisions being brought forward.

Figure 1: Leadership Styles n = 215. Note: Self-reporting is a limitation of this study. Future studies should triangulate observations and staff perceptions of leadership moves to determine leadership style.

Findings Related to Leadership Styles

When considering the different leadership styles in this original small study (n = 260), it cannot be generalized. For this reason, the literature review provided the backdrop for comparison of the data collected. The self-selected participation may have skewed the results in unexpected ways.

The research assumption was made that leadership style would have implications to their job satisfaction, as well as their role and organizational commitment of school administrators in Ontario, Canada, aligning with previously established research. This was surprisingly not the case. Using a definition of different leadership styles, respondents reflected upon what type of leadership they followed. Next, it was compared to their job satisfaction levels as discussed within the interviews and compared to the results of the long-form researcher purpose-built questionnaire data. When speaking within a general interview context, the terms used to define their leadership styles did not directly align to the leadership style definitions posed within the long form. This leads to a question about an individual's understanding about leadership styles. Within the defined leadership types of the quantitative data, leaders were asked, "What form of leadership do they most commonly embark on?" and, "Were they consistent in times of stress or work overload?" After performing a Kruskal-Wallis on key dimensions of the study, no particular pattern was seen. That is to say, despite the identified leadership style, it did not lead to any tendencies for higher levels of wellbeing, job satisfaction, or commitment to stay in the role. Neither did it indicate lower degrees of the nine variables tested. Surprisingly, emotional demands were unaffected consistently across leadership styles. This was an unexpected result. For example, someone who uses a bureaucratic method of leadership would experience no more or less emotional demand in the role than some who led using a consensus or servitude or moral leadership style.

When exploring the connection between the dimensions within the questionnaire and leadership style, a non-patterned influence was presented. Statistical significance is $p = 0.05$ or less. To result in a high correlation, a p value of less than 0.01 would indicate highly correlation

between the variable and the leadership style. A Kruskal-Wallis test was repeated across the dimensions to see if any particular type of pattern arose. Surprising to the author, none did.

Table 2 Leadership Styles of School Administrators – both public and private school leaders

Leadership Style	Dimension Most Influenced by This Particular Leadership Style	P Value
Transformative	The distribution of life balance is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.14
Purposeful Transactional/ Situational	The distribution of work/life balance conflict is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.536
Servitude	The distribution of offensive behaviour is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.074
Consultative	The distribution of health is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.359
Distributive	The distribution of burnout is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.986
Democratic	The distribution of commitment to the organization is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.638
Moral	The distribution of meaningfulness is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.961
Consensus	The distribution of emotional demands is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.742
Bureaucratic	The distribution of intention to stay in the role is the same across categories of leadership style.	0.851
N=215		

The Kruskal-Wallis H test scores were not similar for all groups, as assessed by visual inspection of the boxplot graphs. The distributions of the scores were statistically significantly different between groups, H (7) (degrees of freedom) = 10.996, with a range of *p*-value between 0.140 and 0.986. A pattern would be noted below 0.05. The results found no such patterns and, therefore, there were no links among leadership styles and life balance, offensive behaviour impacts, burnout levels, overall health, organizational commitment, job meaningfulness, positional longevity intention, or emotional demands. Further investigation is warranted to see if this was a study abnormality or if these potential truths could be replicated. If so, then many pushes for leadership change may be less valuable.

The question of leadership style did not impact the key findings that school administrators have strong organizational commitment (mean 3.12, $n = 215$) and an even stronger sense that the work that they do is meaningful (mean 3.35, $n = 215$). Equally notable, life-balance conflict of time (mean 3.14, $n = 215$) shows the negative aspects of the responsibility in the job. The research suggests that a person who decides to enter the role of school administrator will be committed to the organization and find meaning in the challenging work despite the apparent dissatisfiers.

This result more directly aligns with the study's findings around dispositional drivers. Rather than a basis of decision-making leadership style, but their motivational and internal dispositions, a school leader sees different realities. It is concluded that these dispositional drivers more likely determine the imbalance that an individual can maintain between resource needs and positive relatedness variables. Different individuals can endure different situations with varying degrees of strain. Their emotional intelligence, and their connectedness to a guiding belief system will explain why some can stay in the role until meeting a pension target or retirement-age goal and others will not.

The Professionalization of the Role Versus Leadership Style

A small number of publicly funded school administrators directly pointed to the lack of professionalization of the role. This theme surfaced as a dissatisfier for the position. The lack of professionalization of the role leads to major sources of stress, emotional demand, and work overload were related to negative interactions with unreasonable parents. One publicly funded administrator said that parents:

That aren't [supportive] make me to not want to do my job. Instead of aligning with the school, they do not allow their son or daughter to take ownership for the role they played and they make personal attacks on you. They will accuse you of things that never happened, then call your S.O. [supervisory officer] and make abusive comments throughout conversations....

This example explores the desire of a hierarchical leadership structure that would lead parents/caregiver stakeholders to not question their decisions and authority. This respondent names both the structural negatives (calling your supervisor) but laments the lack of respect given for their positional authority. If this is a regular experience within the role, job satisfaction and leadership style both, would be affected.

Degree, intensity, and frequency seemed to differ between the two populations (independent school leaders and publicly funded school principals), leading the researcher to consider this aspect carefully. In short, many publicly funded administrators felt unprotected from the actions of abusive parents, regardless of their leadership approach. Several repeatedly shared feelings of powerlessness and even fear. Words such as “placating,” “avoiding issues,” “wanting it to go away” all arose with frequency to describe their interpreted sense of senior management responses. They expected or accepted violence and disrespect from students at times of high stress, but when parents also partook in this ill-behaviour, administrators noted the additional burden it played on them.

Another aspect of the role that compromises its professionalization is Ontario’s Education Act and its associated legislation. An expectation that school administrators deal with conflict involving students when not at school makes the role’s hours nonconforming. Those that indicated a servitude leadership style, by definition, would struggle in the context of after-hour work linked to technology. The extensive use of social media has added to time demands and the blurring of boundaries. Sadly, it is not just students saying cruel things to students. This abuse is also directed at school administrators. “Dealing with the use of social media by students and parents is exhausting and demoralizing.” Rarely in other professions are the organization leaders responsible for the happenings outside of their sphere of influence. Currently, as a result of tragic deaths from peer-to-peer bullying, this reality makes the job unrelenting, even on weekends and holidays. That sense of 24–7 was a critical source of stress and work overload noted by many interviewed. One early leaver shared the importance of the professionalization of the role:

We need to limit public access to school administrators. Parents should not be able to just walk in to the building and demand to see you. And when told that you are busy, they will not leave until you see them. We need more signage on expectations of how people are to behave. That verbal abuse will not be tolerated. We are so far behind other professions. Just consider, even when you go to the dump, there is signage to say don’t yell at the attendee.

For those school leaders that elected to become a school principal the role to “make a difference”, regardless of their leadership style, is that the trend towards less civility makes the job more difficult. One respondent said, “it doesn’t matter who you are, or how you lead, no one wants to be yelled at for doing what is the right thing to do. Parents want the exception to

be made for their child and the other child to be punished”. This publicly funded administrator felt that the process of professionalizing the role could be replicated from others successful fields. What has become commonplace, is negatively impacting the work that school leaders are able to perform.

Leadership Styles Do Not Impact Job Satisfaction Among Publicly-Funded Administrators

One of the most interesting findings of this study was that leadership style did not influence job satisfaction in any notable way, particularly for publicly-funded school administrators. For this analysis the type of leadership was not separated out, but as you can see below, regardless of the leadership style, there was high job satisfaction. This was not as evident for privately-funded school leaders. (Further investigation for the privately-funded school administration group is warranted).

Table 3

Publicly Funded School Administrator Respondents – Pearson Correlation between Emotion Demands and Job Satisfaction

Correlations			
		My work is emotionally demanding.	Considering all the realities, I am highly satisfied with my job.
My work is emotionally demanding.	Pearson Correlation	1	.996**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	182	182
Considering all the realities, I am highly satisfied with my job.	Pearson Correlation	.996**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	182	182
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Across all leadership types, no style had the strongest connection to job satisfaction. As seen in the previous tables, job satisfaction seemed unwavering across school contexts, stage of career, emotional demands, the degree of unionization, or the challenges faced daily. These results contradict larger studies that link leadership style with job satisfaction, life balance, emotional demands, or leaving rates.

Conclusions

The approach to leadership within schools is a complex task. The rapid succession of demands with increasing regularity of school leaders globally. In Ontario, Canada, these realities bring into question if leadership style can act as an insulating factor to the demands of the role. Too many school administrators are leaving the role, and fewer teachers are aspiring to join the ranks. Therefore, carefully understanding how school principals lead, and how that leadership influences job satisfaction for both the leaders, themselves, and their staff is a valuable endeavour. This study sought to confirm findings within in larger province-based studies and studies from similar educational contexts globally. The questions explored were: Does a principal's leadership style influence their job satisfaction? Do specific types of leadership styles lead to stronger organizational commitments? Do specific leadership styles of school leaders change the experience of emotional labour / emotional drain? The findings from this small mixed method study (n=215 quantitative, n=45 qualitative) had unexpected results.

In this small study, leadership styles did not influence job satisfaction. The majority of school leaders saw value in their role and through that had higher levels of job satisfaction than other professions. The dissatisfiers of the job impacted all leaders, regardless of their approach. Non-patterned results showed that dissatisfiers take a heavy toll across leadership types. The larger studies showed that different forms leadership does matter for leaders and their schools. Forms of distributive leadership enhances the level of staff satisfaction, tempers workload and potentially provides school leaders with a stronger sense of community (Heenan et al., 2024). Transformative leadership practices create the strongest sense of self within the role and that translate to stronger retention levels of principals (Heenan et al., 2024). Culturally responsiveness increased with purposeful/situational leadership and servitude leadership practices (Eva & Sendjaya, 2024). Mentorship of school leaders is important to reinforce the healthiest approaches for our school communities (Hickey et al., 2022).

Finally, it can be lost that the being a school principal or vice principal is a daunting task. Education settings, post-pandemic, is even more complex, with a combination of lagging skill development in children, more complex learning profiles and a seemingly less patient society as a whole (Chatzipanagiotou & Katsarou, 2023). As principals engage in the role of leadership they are stretched daily. Competing interests makes the pace and intricacy of tasks sometimes overwhelming. Leadership styles vary in their effectiveness based partially on the context in which they are employed. When a principal approaches a situation with the “right” style, great things can happen. When they approach it with a style that is not the “right fit” than the job becomes less satisfying and more arduous. This, will in turn impact the leader’s effectiveness and wellbeing.

Further research in a comparison amongst various leadership styles and the influence that dissatisfiers have on the principal’s experience as school leader should be sought. Many questions around varying definitions of leadership styles overlap; making direct comparison difficult across studies. Self-reporting versus teacher perceptions confounds the observations and the interpretation of what motivated school leaders. The role of the school principal is essential to educational system stability, progress and overall wellbeing for students, leaders and staff. Without a clear understanding what supports school progress while maintaining the health of the school leader -- the ongoing leadership crisis in our schools will continue.

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